
Clinical Study Report Appendix 12.1.2

Drug Substance Rosuvastatin

Study Code D3560L00030
(4522US/0011)

**Appendix 12.1.2
Sample Case Report Form**

Section 5.3.5.1.1 /p.1

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Visit No. 1

Visit

VISITCR

Visit date
year mm dd

Demography

DEMCR

P Date of birth
year mm dd

Sex

Male
Female

Origin

Caucasian
Black (complete sub-group below)
Asian (complete sub-group below)
Hispanic
Other (complete sub-group below)

Origin and Sub-group

Black Sub-group

African
African-American
African-Caribbean
Other

Asian Sub-group

Japanese
Chinese/East Asian
South Asian (Indian sub-continent)
Other

Other Sub-group

American Indian/ Alaska Native
Native Hawaiian/ Pacific Islander
Other

Consent

Date of written consent
year mm dd

Date of written genomics consent
year mm dd

Education

EDUCR

≤ High School Some College College Graduate Post Graduate

2003-02-12

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Visit No. 1

Visit

VISITCR

Visit date 2 0
year mm dd

Demography

DEMCR

Date of birth 1 9
year mm dd

Sex

Male
Female

Origin

Caucasian
Black (complete sub-group below)
Asian (complete sub-group below)
Hispanic
Other (complete sub-group below)

Origin and Sub-group

Black Sub-group

African
African-American
African-Caribbean
Other

Asian Sub-group

Japanese
Chinese/East Asian
South Asian (Indian sub-continent)
Other

Other Sub-group

American Indian/ Alaska Native
Native Hawaiian/ Pacific Islander
Other

Consent

Date of initial written consent 2 0
year mm dd

Date of written genomics consent 2 0
year mm dd

Education

EDUCR

≤ High School Some College College Graduate Post Graduate

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Visit No. 1

Exercise

EXERCR

Indicate frequency of strenuous exercise (e.g. swimming, aerobics, cycling, running)

Rarely / never	☐	2-3 times a week	☐
<once a week	☐	4-6 times a week	☐
once a week	☐	daily	☐

Alcohol

ALCCR

Indicate average use during the past year
 (1 drink = 12 oz (360 ml) beer = 4 oz (120 ml) wine = 1 1/2 oz (45 ml) spirits)

Never or <1 drink/month	☐	1-3 drinks per day	☐
1-3 drinks per month	☐	4-5 drinks per day	☐
1-4 drinks per week	☐	6+ drinks per day	☐
5-6 drinks per week	☐		

Laboratory Assessment

LABCR

Fasting blood sample date
year mm dd

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Visit No. 2

Visit

VISITCR

Visit date
year mm dd

Eligibility Criteria

CRITCR

Did the Subject meet all eligibility criteria?	☐ No	☐ Yes	
If No, specify the failed criteria	☐ Incl	☐ Excl	Criteria # <input type="text"/>
	☐	☐	<input type="text"/>
	☐	☐	<input type="text"/>

Vital Signs, Weight, Height, Waist Circumference

VITCR

Pulse, sitting beats/min

Blood pressure, sitting / mmHg
systolic diastolic

Weight lb OR kg

Height in OR cm

Waist circumference in OR cm

Laboratory Assessment

LABCR

Fasting blood sample date
year mm dd

Urine sample date
year mm dd

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Visit No. 2

Significant Medical History

HISMCR

Does the Subject have any significant medical history or current medical conditions? No Yes

NOTE: If Subject is female and is post-menopausal or has been surgically sterilized, please indicate as a medical history record.

Description of Condition (one per line)	Past (not currently active)	Current* (ongoing)
	Yes	Yes
1. _____	☐	☐
2. _____	☐	☐
3. _____	☐	☐
4. _____	☐	☐
5. _____	☐	☐
6. _____	☐	☐
7. _____	☐	☐
8. _____	☐	☐
9. _____	☐	☐
10. _____	☐	☐
11. _____	☐	☐
12. _____	☐	☐
13. _____	☐	☐
14. _____	☐	☐
15. _____	☐	☐
16. _____	☐	☐
17. _____	☐	☐
18. _____	☐	☐

*NOTE: If Subject is receiving any medication therapy for the above current conditions, please record on Concomitant Therapy CRF.

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Visit No. 2

Physical Examination

PHYSCR

Indicate (✓) Normal or Abnormal

Specification of abnormalities Only

	Normal	Abnormal	
General Appearance	☐	☐	
Skin	☐	☐	
EENT	☐	☐	
Lymph Nodes	☐	☐	
Endocrine	☐	☐	
Musculoskeletal	☐	☐	
Cardiovascular	☐	☐	
Respiratory	☐	☐	
Central Nervous System	☐	☐	
Gastrointestinal	☐	☐	

Family History Stroke and Diabetes

FAMHISCR

Did either natural parent ever have a stroke?

	No	Yes	Unknown	
Mother	☐	☐	☐	If Yes, specify age <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/>
Father	☐	☐	☐	If Yes, specify age <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/>

Did any of these blood relatives ever have diabetes?

	No	Yes	Unknown	
Mother	☐	☐	☐	
Father	☐	☐	☐	
Sister	☐	☐	☐	If Yes, total # of sisters <input type="text"/> Total # with diabetes <input type="text"/>
Brother	☐	☐	☐	If Yes, total # of brothers <input type="text"/> Total # with diabetes <input type="text"/>

Amended 2006-01-31

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials

F	M	L

Subject No.

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Centre No.

--	--	--	--

Visit No. 2

Major Risk Factors

RISKCR

	No	Yes		
Cigarette smoking (in the last month)	☐	☐		
If Yes, mean number of cigarettes per day	<table border="1" style="display: inline-table; border-collapse: collapse;"><tr><td style="width: 20px; height: 20px;"></td><td style="width: 20px; height: 20px;"></td></tr></table>			
Hypertension (BP $\geq$ 140/90 mmHg or on antihypertensive medication)	☐	☐		
Family history of premature CHD (CHD in male first-degree relative <55 years; CHD in female first-degree relative <65 years)	☐	☐		

Bone Fracture

BONECR

Has the Subject ever had a bone fracture?	No	Yes			
	☐	☐			
If Yes:	Hip	☐	Vertebral		
	Wrist	☐	Other		
	Ankle	☐	☐		
Number of incidences in the past 20 years the Subject has broken 1 or more bones		<table border="1" style="display: inline-table; border-collapse: collapse;"><tr><td style="width: 20px; height: 20px;"></td><td style="width: 20px; height: 20px;"></td></tr></table>			(For example: Car accident with multiple breaks would count as 1 incident)

Run-In Phase Study Medication

SACCR

Dispensing Accountability at Visit 2

Date dispensed

2	0			
year	mm	dd		

 Number of tablets dispensed

--	--	--	--

Medication Bottle Labels

Please attach label from medication dispensed at this visit

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Visit No. 3

Visit

VISITCR

Visit date 2 0
year mm dd

Randomization Criteria

CRITCR

Does the Subject continue to meet randomization and compliance criteria? No Yes

If No, specify the failed criteria

☐	Incl	☐	Excl	<input type="text"/>	Criteria #
☐	Incl	☐	Excl	<input type="text"/>	Criteria #
☐	Incl	☐	Excl	<input type="text"/>	Criteria #

If Yes, complete Visit 3. Please randomize and enter the assigned randomization number

Run-in Phase Study Medication

SACCR

Return Accountability from Visit 2

Date returned 2 0
year mm dd

Number of tablets returned

Randomized Phase Study Medication

Dispensing Accountability at Visit 3

Date dispensed 2 0
year mm dd

Number of tablets dispensed

Medication Bottle Labels

Please attach label from medication dispensed at this visit

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials

F	M	L

Subject No.

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Centre No.

--	--	--	--	--

Visit No. 4

Visit

VISITCR

Visit date

2	0				
year		mm		dd	

Visit Type

VISTYP

Type of visit Office Telephone

Laboratory Assessment

LABCR

Blood sample date

2	0				
year		mm		dd	

Urine sample date

2	0				
year		mm		dd	

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Visit No. 4

Study Medication

SACCR

Subject discontinued study medication No Yes
If Yes, specify discontinuation reason below

- Clinical Event
- Initiation of open label statin therapy
- Adverse Event, Specify:
- Other, Specify:

Return Accountability from Visit 3

Date returned 2 0
year mm dd Number of tablets returned

Dispensing Accountability at Visit 4

Date dispensed 2 0
year mm dd Number of tablets dispensed

Medication Bottle Label

Please attach label
from medication
dispensed at this
visit

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Visit No. 5

Visit

VISITCR

Visit date 2 0
year mm dd

Visit Type

VISTYP

Type of visit Office Telephone

Laboratory Assessment

LABCR

Blood sample date 2 0
year mm dd

Urine sample date 2 0
year mm dd

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Visit No. 5

Study Medication

SACCR

Subject discontinued study medication

No Yes

If Yes, specify discontinuation reason below

- Clinical Event
- Initiation of open label statin therapy
- Adverse Event, Specify:
- Other, Specify:

Return Accountability from Visit 4

Date returned 2 0
year mm dd

Number of tablets returned

Dispensing Accountability at Visit 5

Date dispensed 2 0
year mm dd

Number of tablets dispensed

Medication Bottle Label

Please attach label from medication dispensed at this visit

Please attach label from medication dispensed at this visit

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Visit No. 5.1

NM04:02

Telephone Contact, 3 Month Interim Contact

TELCON

Date of successful telephone contact with Subject 2 0
year mm dd

 If Subject experienced any new adverse events since the last visit, please record on Adverse Events CRF

 If Subject experienced any new clinical events since the last visit, please record on appropriate Clinical Endpoint CRF

 If Subject stopped taking any concomitant medications or began taking any new concomitant medications since the last visit, please record on the Concomitant Therapy CRF.

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Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials

F	M	L	

Subject No.

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Centre No.

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Visit No. 6

Visit

VISITCR

Visit date

2	0				
year		mm		dd	

Visit Type

VISTYP

Type of visit

Office	Telephone
☐	☐

Laboratory Assessment

LABCR

Fasting blood sample date

2	0				
year		mm		dd	

Urine sample date

2	0				
year		mm		dd	

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Visit No. 6

Study Medication

SACCR

Subject discontinued study medication

No

Yes

If Yes, specify discontinuation reason below

Clinical Event

Initiation of open label statin therapy

Adverse Event, Specify:

Other, Specify:

Return Accountability from Visit 5

Date returned

2 0
year mm dd

Number of tablets returned

Dispensing Accountability at Visit 6

Date dispensed

2 0
year mm dd

Number of tablets dispensed

Medication Bottle Label

Please attach label from medication dispensed at this visit

Please attach label from medication dispensed at this visit

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Visit No. 6.1

NM04-02

Telephone Contact, 3 Month Interim Contact

TELCON

Date of successful telephone contact with Subject
year mm dd

 If Subject experienced any new adverse events since the last visit, please record on Adverse Events CRF

 If Subject experienced any new clinical events since the last visit, please record on appropriate Clinical Endpoint CRF

 If Subject stopped taking any concomitant medications or began taking any new concomitant medications since the last visit, please record on the Concomitant Therapy CRF.

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Visit No. 7

Visit

VISITCR

Visit date 2 0
year mm dd

Visit Type

VISTYP

Type of visit Office Telephone

Laboratory Assessment

LABCR

Blood sample date 2 0
year mm dd

Urine sample date 2 0
year mm dd

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Visit No. 7

Study Medication

SACCR

Subject discontinued study medication

No Yes

If Yes, specify discontinuation reason below

- Clinical Event
- Initiation of open label statin therapy
- Adverse Event, Specify:
- Other, Specify:

Return Accountability from Visit 6

Date returned 2 0
year mm dd

Number of tablets returned

Dispensing Accountability at Visit 7

Date dispensed 2 0
year mm dd

Number of tablets dispensed

Medication Bottle Label

Please attach label from medication dispensed at this visit

Please attach label from medication dispensed at this visit

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Visit No. 7.1

NW04-02

Telephone Contact, 3 Month Interim Contact

TELCON

Date of successful telephone contact with Subject
year mm dd

 If Subject experienced any new adverse events since the last visit, please record on Adverse Events CRF

 If Subject experienced any new clinical events since the last visit, please record on appropriate Clinical Endpoint CRF

 If Subject stopped taking any concomitant medications or began taking any new concomitant medications since the last visit, please record on the Concomitant Therapy CRF.

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials

F	M	L

Subject No.

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Centre No.

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Visit No. 8

Visit

VISITCR

Visit date

2	0				
year	mm	dd			

Visit Type

VISTYP

Type of visit

Office	☐	Telephone	☐
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Laboratory Assessment

LABCR

Fasting blood sample date

2	0				
year	mm	dd			

Urine sample date

2	0				
year	mm	dd			

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Visit No. 8

Study Medication

SACCR

Subject discontinued study medication

No Yes

If Yes, specify discontinuation reason below

- Clinical Event
- Initiation of open label statin therapy
- Adverse Event, Specify:
- Other, Specify:

Return Accountability from Visit 7

Date returned 2 0
year mm dd

Number of tablets returned

Dispensing Accountability at Visit 8

Date dispensed 2 0
year mm dd

Number of tablets dispensed

Medication Bottle Label

Please attach label from medication dispensed at this visit

Please attach label from medication dispensed at this visit

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Visit No. 8.1

NIM04:02

Telephone Contact, 3 Month Interim Contact

TELCON

Date of successful telephone contact with Subject
year mm dd

 If Subject experienced any new adverse events since the last visit, please record on Adverse Events CRF

 If Subject experienced any new clinical events since the last visit, please record on appropriate Clinical Endpoint CRF

 If Subject stopped taking any concomitant medications or began taking any new concomitant medications since the last visit, please record on the Concomitant Therapy CRF.

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials [][] [][]
F M L

Subject No. [][][][]

Centre No. [][][][]

Visit No. 9

Visit

VISIT

Visit date [2 | 0 |] [][] [][]
year mm dd

Visit Type

VISTYP

Type of visit Office Telephone

Laboratory Assessment

LABCR

Blood sample date [2 | 0 |] [][] [][]
year mm dd

Urine sample date [2 | 0 |] [][] [][]
year mm dd

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Visit No. 9

Study Medication

SACCR

Subject discontinued study medication

No Yes

If Yes, specify discontinuation reason below

- Clinical Event
- Initiation of open label statin therapy
- Adverse Event, Specify:
- Other, Specify:

Return Accountability from Visit 8

Date returned 2 0
year mm dd

Number of tablets returned

Dispensing Accountability at Visit 9

Date dispensed 2 0
year mm dd

Number of tablets dispensed

Medication Bottle Label

Please attach label from medication dispensed at this visit

Please attach label from medication dispensed at this visit

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Visit No. 9.1

NM04-02

Telephone Contact, 3 Month Interim Contact

TELCON

Date of successful telephone contact with Subject
year mm dd

 If Subject experienced any new adverse events since the last visit, please record on Adverse Events CRF

 If Subject experienced any new clinical events since the last visit, please record on appropriate Clinical Endpoint CRF

 If Subject stopped taking any concomitant medications or began taking any new concomitant medications since the last visit, please record on the Concomitant Therapy CRF.

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials

F	M	L

Subject No.

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Centre No.

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Visit No. 10

Visit

VISITCR

Visit date

2	0				
year	mm	dd			

Visit Type

VISTYP

Type of visit Office Telephone

Laboratory Assessment

LABCR

Fasting blood sample date

2	0				
year	mm	dd			

Urine sample date

2	0				
year	mm	dd			

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Visit No. 10

Study Medication

SACCR

Subject discontinued study medication

No Yes

If Yes, specify discontinuation reason below

- Clinical Event
- Initiation of open label statin therapy
- Adverse Event, Specify:
- Other, Specify:

Return Accountability from Visit 9

Date returned 2 0
year mm dd

Number of tablets returned

Dispensing Accountability at Visit 10

Date dispensed 2 0
year mm dd

Number of tablets dispensed

Medication Bottle Label

Please attach label from medication dispensed at this visit

Please attach label from medication dispensed at this visit

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Visit No. 10.1

NM04-02

Telephone Contact, 3 Month Interim Contact

TELCON

Date of successful telephone contact with Subject
year mm dd

 If Subject experienced any new adverse events since the last visit, please record on Adverse Events CRF

 If Subject experienced any new clinical events since the last visit, please record on appropriate Clinical Endpoint CRF

 If Subject stopped taking any concomitant medications or began taking any new concomitant medications since the last visit, please record on the Concomitant Therapy CRF.

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Final Visit

Visit

VISITCR

Visit date 2 0
year mm dd

Visit Type

VISTYP

Type of visit Office Telephone

Vital Signs, Weight, Waist circumference

VITCR

Pulse, sitting beats/min

Blood pressure, sitting / mmHg
systolic diastolic

Weight lb OR kg

Waist circumference in OR cm

Laboratory Assessment

LABCR

Fasting blood sample date 2 0
year mm dd

Urine sample date 2 0
year mm dd

Study Medication

SACCR

Return Accountability from Visit

Date returned 2 0
year mm dd

Number of tablets returned

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials

F	M	L

Subject No.

--	--	--	--

Centre No.

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Final Visit

Physical Examination

PHYSCR

Indicate (✓) Normal, Abnormal, or New or Aggravated

	Normal	Abnormal (Same as Visit 2)	New or Aggravated	<i>Describe NEW or AGGRAVATED Abnormalities Only</i>
General Appearance	☐	☐	☐	
Skin	☐	☐	☐	
EENT	☐	☐	☐	
Lymph Nodes	☐	☐	☐	
Endocrine	☐	☐	☐	
Musculoskeletal	☐	☐	☐	
Cardiovascular	☐	☐	☐	
Respiratory	☐	☐	☐	
Central Nervous System	☐	☐	☐	
Gastrointestinal	☐	☐	☐	

NOTE: Record condition of all New or Aggravated Abnormalities on the Adverse Events CRF.

Amended 2006-01-31

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials

F	M	L

Subject No.

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Centre No.

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Study Completion/Withdrawal

TERMCR

Date of Study completion/withdrawal

2	0				
year	mm	dd			

Date of last dose

2	0				
year	mm	dd			

Specify primary reason for study completion/withdrawal:

- Completed study as planned
- Subject withdrew consent due to Adverse Event Please complete the Adverse Event form
- Subject withdrew consent due to reason other than Adverse Event
- Subject lost to follow-up
- Other Please specify

Statement of Death

Date of death

2	0				
year	mm	dd			

Was a postmortem performed

No	Yes
☐	☐

Cause of death _____

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Principal Investigator's Signature

SIGNCR

The investigator's signature on this page verifies that he/she has reviewed all data recorded on the case report form pages.

The investigator has also reviewed all laboratory findings throughout the study and has reported all laboratory findings considered Adverse Events in accordance with protocol guidance as clinically appropriate.

year mm dd Principal Investigator's signature

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials

F	M	L

Subject No.

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Centre No.

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Visit No. 2

Significant Medical History

HISMCR

NOTE: If Subject is female and is post-menopausal or has been surgically sterilized, please indicate as a medical history record.

Description of Condition (one per line)	Past (not currently active)	Current* (ongoing)
	Yes	Yes
1. _____	☐	☐
2. _____	☐	☐
3. _____	☐	☐
4. _____	☐	☐
5. _____	☐	☐
6. _____	☐	☐
7. _____	☐	☐
8. _____	☐	☐
9. _____	☐	☐
10. _____	☐	☐
11. _____	☐	☐
12. _____	☐	☐
13. _____	☐	☐
14. _____	☐	☐
15. _____	☐	☐
16. _____	☐	☐
17. _____	☐	☐
18. _____	☐	☐

***NOTE:** If Subject is receiving any medication therapy for the above current conditions, please record on Concomitant Therapy CRF.

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials

F	M	L

Subject No.

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Centre No.

--	--	--	--	--

Visit No. ___

Visit

VISITCR

Visit date

2	0				
year	mm	dd			

Visit Type

VISTYP

Type of visit Office Telephone

Laboratory Assessment

LABCR

Fasting blood sample date

2	0				
year	mm	dd			

Urine sample date

2	0				
year	mm	dd			

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Visit No. ____

Study Medication

SACCR

Subject discontinued study medication

No Yes

If Yes, specify discontinuation reason below

- Clinical Event
- Initiation of open label statin therapy
- Adverse Event, Specify:
- Other, Specify:

Return Accountability from Visit ____

Date returned

2 0
year mm dd

Number of tablets returned

Dispensing Accountability at Visit ____

Date dispensed

2 0
year mm dd

Number of tablets dispensed

Medication Bottle Label

Please attach label from medication dispensed at this visit

Please attach label from medication dispensed at this visit

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Visit No. ____1

NIM0402

Telephone Contact, 3 Month Interim Contact

TELCON

Date of successful telephone contact with Subject
21 01 year mm dd

 If Subject experienced any new adverse events since the last visit, please record on Adverse Events CRF

 If Subject experienced any new clinical events since the last visit, please record on appropriate Clinical Endpoint CRF

 If Subject stopped taking any concomitant medications or began taking any new concomitant medications since the last visit, please record on the Concomitant Therapy CRF.

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Visit No. ___

Visit

VISITCR

Visit date 2 0
year mm dd

Unscheduled Laboratory Assessment

LABCR

Fasting blood sample date 2 0
year mm dd

Urine sample date 2 0
year mm dd

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Visit No. ____

Visit

VISITCR

Visit date 2 0
year mm dd

Unscheduled Study Medication

SACCR

Return Accountability from Visit ____

Date returned 2 0
year mm dd

Number of tablets returned

Dispensing Accountability at Visit ____

Date dispensed 2 0
year mm dd

Number of tablets dispensed

Medication Bottle Label

Please attach label
 from medication
 dispensed at this
 visit

Please attach label
 from medication
 dispensed at this
 visit

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials

F	M	L	

Subject No.

--	--	--	--	--	--

Centre No.

--	--	--	--	--	--

Visit No. ___

Visit

VISITCR

Visit date

2	0						
year		mm		dd			

Unscheduled Visit Type

VISTYP

Subject Transfer
Final Evaluation at
Site A

Subject Transfer
Initial Evaluation at
Site B

Other

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials

F	M	L

Subject No.

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Centre No.

--	--	--	--

Visit No. 1

Exercise

EXERCR

Indicate frequency of strenuous exercise (e.g. swimming, aerobics, cycling, running)

Rarely / never	☐	2-3 times a week	☐
<once a week	☐	4-6 times a week	☐
once a week	☐	daily	☐

Alcohol

ALCCR

Indicate average use during the past year (1 drink = 12 oz. beer = 4 oz. wine = 1 1/2 oz spirits)

Never or <1 drink/month	☐	1-3 drinks per day	☐
1-3 drinks per month	☐	4-5 drinks per day	☐
1-4 drinks per week	☐	6+ drinks per day	☐
5-6 drinks per week	☐		

Laboratory Assessment

LABCR

Fasting blood sample date

2	0	0			
year			mm	dd	

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Visit No. 1

Exercise

EXERCR

Indicate frequency of strenuous exercise (e.g. swimming, aerobics, cycling, running)

Rarely / never	☐	2-3 times a week	☐
<once a week	☐	4-6 times a week	☐
once a week	☐	daily	☐

Alcohol

ALCCR

Indicate average use during the past year
 (1 drink = 12 oz (360 ml) beer = 4 oz (120 ml) wine = 1 1/2 oz (45 ml) spirits)

Never or <1 drink/month	☐	1-3 drinks per day	☐
1-3 drinks per month	☐	4-5 drinks per day	☐
1-4 drinks per week	☐	6+ drinks per day	☐
5-6 drinks per week	☐		

Laboratory Assessment

LABCR

Fasting blood sample date
year mm dd

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Visit No. 2

Visit

VISITCR

Visit date
year mm dd

Eligibility Criteria

CRITCR

Did the Subject meet all eligibility criteria?	No	Yes	
	☐	☐	
If No, specify the failed criteria	Incl	Excl	Criteria #
	☐	☐	<input type="text"/> <input type="text"/>
	☐	☐	<input type="text"/> <input type="text"/>
	☐	☐	<input type="text"/> <input type="text"/>

Vital Signs, Weight, Height, Waist Circumference

VITCR

Pulse, sitting beats/min

Blood pressure, sitting / mmHg
systolic diastolic

Weight lb OR kg

Height in OR cm

Waist circumference in OR cm

Laboratory Assessment

LABCR

Fasting blood sample date
year mm dd

Urine sample date
year mm dd

Amended 2005-03-08

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Final Visit

Visit

VISITCR

Visit date
year mm dd

Vital Signs, Weight, Waist circumference

VITCR

Pulse, sitting beats/min

Blood pressure, sitting / mmHg
systolic diastolic

Weight lb OR kg

Waist circumference in OR cm

Laboratory Assessment

LABCR

Fasting blood sample date
year mm dd

Urine sample date
year mm dd

Study Medication

SACCR

Return Accountability from Visit ___

Date returned
year mm dd

Number of tablets returned

Amended 2005-03-08

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Visit No. 2

Visit

VISITCR

Visit date 2 0 0
year mm dd

Eligibility Criteria

CRITCR

Did the Subject meet all eligibility criteria?	No	Yes	
	☐	☐	
If No, specify the failed criteria	Incl	Excl	Criteria #
	☐	☐	<input type="text"/> <input type="text"/>
	☐	☐	<input type="text"/> <input type="text"/>
	☐	☐	<input type="text"/> <input type="text"/>

Vital Signs, Weight, Height, Waist Circumference

VITCR

Pulse, sitting beats/min

Blood pressure, sitting / mmHg
systolic diastolic

Weight lb

Height in

Waist circumference in

Laboratory Assessment

LABCR

Fasting blood sample date 2 0 0
year mm dd

Urine sample date 2 0 0
year mm dd

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Visit No. 2

Significant Medical History

HISMCR

Does the Subject have any significant medical history or current medical conditions? No Yes

NOTE: If Subject is female and is post-menopausal or has been surgically sterilized, please indicate as a medical history record.

Description of Condition (one per line)	Past (not currently active)	Current* (ongoing)
	Yes	Yes
1. _____	☐	☐
2. _____	☐	☐
3. _____	☐	☐
4. _____	☐	☐
5. _____	☐	☐
6. _____	☐	☐
7. _____	☐	☐
8. _____	☐	☐
9. _____	☐	☐
10. _____	☐	☐
11. _____	☐	☐
12. _____	☐	☐
13. _____	☐	☐
14. _____	☐	☐
15. _____	☐	☐
16. _____	☐	☐
17. _____	☐	☐
18. _____	☐	☐

***NOTE:** If Subject is receiving any medication therapy for the above current conditions, please record on **Concomitant Therapy** form.

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Visit No. 2

Physical Examination

PHYSCR

Indicate (✓) Normal or Abnormal

Specification of abnormalities Only

	Normal	Abnormal	
General Appearance	☐	☐	
Skin	☐	☐	
EENT	☐	☐	
Lymph Nodes	☐	☐	
Endocrine	☐	☐	
Musculoskeletal	☐	☐	
Cardiovascular	☐	☐	
Respiratory	☐	☐	
Central Nervous System	☐	☐	
Gastrointestinal	☐	☐	

NOTE: Record the condition of all Abnormalities on the **Medical History** form.

Family History Stroke and Diabetes

FAMHISCR

Did either natural parent ever have a stroke?

	No	Yes	Unknown	
Mother	☐	☐	☐	If Yes, specify age <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/>
Father	☐	☐	☐	If Yes, specify age <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/>

Did any of these blood relatives ever have diabetes?

	No	Yes	Unknown	
Mother	☐	☐	☐	
Father	☐	☐	☐	
Sister	☐	☐	☐	If Yes, total # of sisters <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> Total # with diabetes <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/>
Brother	☐	☐	☐	If Yes, total # of brothers <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> Total # with diabetes <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/>

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Visit No. 2

Major Risk Factors

RISKCR

Cigarette smoking (in the last month)

No Yes

If Yes, mean number of cigarettes per day

Hypertension (BP $\geq$ 140/90 mmHg or on antihypertensive medication)

No Yes

Family history of premature CHD (CHD in male first-degree relative <55 years;
 CHD in female first-degree relative <65 years)

Bone Fracture

BONECR

Has the Subject ever had a bone fracture? No Yes

If Yes: Hip Vertebral
 Wrist Other
 Ankle

Number of incidences in the past 20 years the Subject has broken 1 or more bones (For example: Car accident with multiple breaks would count as 1 incident)

Run-In Phase Study Medication

SACCR

Dispensing Accountability at Visit 2

Date dispensed
year mm dd

Number of tablets dispensed

Medication Bottle Labels

Please attach label from medication dispensed at this visit

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Visit No. 3

Visit

VISITCR

Visit date
year mm dd

Randomization Criteria

CRITCR

Does the Subject continue to meet randomization and compliance criteria? No Yes

If No, specify the failed criteria

☐	Incl	☐	Excl	<input type="text"/>	Criteria #
☐	Incl	☐	Excl	<input type="text"/>	Criteria #
☐	Incl	☐	Excl	<input type="text"/>	Criteria #
☐	Incl	☐	Excl	<input type="text"/>	Criteria #

If Yes, complete Visit 3. Please randomize and enter the assigned randomization number

Run-in Phase Study Medication

SACCR

Return Accountability from Visit 2

Date returned
year mm dd

Number of tablets returned

Randomized Phase Study Medication

Dispensing Accountability at Visit 3

Date dispensed
year mm dd

Number of tablets dispensed

Medication Bottle Labels

Please attach label
from medication
dispensed at this
visit

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials

F	M	L

Subject No.

--	--	--	--	--

Centre No.

--	--	--	--	--

Visit No. 3

Visit

VISITCR

Visit date

2	0	0			
year	mm	dd			

Randomization Criteria

CRITCR

	No	Yes							
Does the Subject continue to meet randomization and compliance criteria?	☐	☐							
	Incl	Excl	Criteria #						
If No, specify the failed criteria	☐	☐	<table border="1" style="display: inline-table; vertical-align: middle;"><tr><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td></tr></table>						
	☐	☐	<table border="1" style="display: inline-table; vertical-align: middle;"><tr><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td></tr></table>						
	☐	☐	<table border="1" style="display: inline-table; vertical-align: middle;"><tr><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td></tr></table>						
If Yes, complete Visit 3. Please randomize and enter the assigned randomization number			<table border="1" style="display: inline-table; vertical-align: middle;"><tr><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td></tr></table>						

Run-in Phase Study Medication

SACCR

Return Accountability from Visit 2

Date returned

2	0	0			
year	mm	dd			

Number of tablets returned

--	--	--	--

Randomized Phase Study Medication

Dispensing Accountability at Visit 3

Date dispensed

2	0	0			
year	mm	dd			

Number of tablets dispensed

--	--	--	--

Medication Bottle Labels

Please attach label from medication dispensed at this visit

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials

F	M	L

Subject No.

--	--	--	--	--

Centre No.

--	--	--	--	--

Demography

SDEMCR

Date of birth

year	mm	dd		

Date of written consent

year	mm	dd		

Sex

Male
Female

Origin

Caucasian
Black
Asian
Hispanic
Other

Study Withdrawal

STERMCR

Date of withdrawal

2	0	0			
year	mm	dd			

Did the Subject have any serious adverse events? No Yes If Yes, complete the Adverse Event form

Check primary reason for withdrawal

		Number of first failed criterion	Criteria #	Incl	Excl	
Subject did not meet inclusion/exclusion criteria	☐		<table border="1" style="display: inline-table; border-collapse: collapse;"><tr><td style="width: 20px; height: 20px;"></td></tr></table>		☐	☐
Adverse event (including clinical endpoint)	☐					
Protocol noncompliance (protocol deviation)	☐					
Subject withdrew consent	☐					
Subject lost to follow-up	☐					
Investigator's discretion	☐					
Other	☐	Please specify				

Investigator's Signature

SSIGNCR

By signing and dating this page, I declare that the information on this CRF and all laboratory data have been reviewed by me or my authorized delegate, and is accurate and complete.

2	0	0			
year	mm	dd			

Investigator's signature

2003-11-06

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Visit No. 3

Visit

VISITCR

Visit date 2 0 0
year mm dd

Randomization Criteria

CRITCR

Does the Subject continue to meet randomization and compliance criteria? No Yes

If No, specify the failed criteria

Incl	Excl	Criteria #
☐	☐	<input type="text"/>
Incl	Excl	Criteria #
☐	☐	<input type="text"/>
Incl	Excl	Criteria #
☐	☐	<input type="text"/>

If Yes, complete Visit 3. Please randomize and enter the assigned randomization number

Run-in Phase Study Medication

SACCR

Return Accountability from Visit 2

Date returned 2 0 0
year mm dd

Number of tablets returned

Randomized Phase Study Medication

Dispensing Accountability at Visit 3

Date dispensed 2 0 0
year mm dd

Number of tablets dispensed

Medication Bottle Labels

Please attach label
from medication
dispensed at this
visit

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Demography

SDEMCR

Date of birth
year mm dd

Date of written consent
year mm dd

Sex
Male
Female

Origin
Caucasian
Black
Asian
Hispanic
Other

Study Withdrawal

STERMCR

Date of withdrawal
year mm dd

Did the Subject have any serious adverse events? No Yes If Yes, complete the Adverse Event form

Check primary reason for withdrawal

		Inclusion Criteria #	Exclusion Criteria #
Subject did not meet inclusion/exclusion criteria	☐	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Adverse event (including clinical endpoint)	☐		
Protocol noncompliance (protocol deviation)	☐		
Subject withdrew consent	☐		
Subject lost to follow-up	☐		
Investigator's discretion	☐		
Other	☐		

Number of first failed criterion

Please specify

Investigator's Signature

SSIGNCR

By signing and dating this page, I declare that the information on this CRF and all laboratory data have been reviewed by me or my authorized delegate, and is accurate and complete.

year mm dd Investigator's signature

2004.02.09

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials

F	M	L

Subject No.

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Centre No.

--	--	--	--	--

Visit No. 4

Visit

VISITCR

Visit date

2	0	0			
year	mm	dd			

Laboratory Assessment

LABCR

Fasting blood sample date

2	0	0			
year	mm	dd			

Urine sample date

2	0	0			
year	mm	dd			

Study Medication

SACCR

Subject has discontinued study medication due to:

- Study medication has not been discontinued (provide dispensing data below)
- Endpoint
- Initiation of open label statin therapy
- Other reason

Return Accountability from Visit 3

Date returned

2	0	0			
year	mm	dd			

 Number of tablets returned

--	--	--	--

Dispensing Accountability at Visit 4

Date dispensed

2	0	0			
year	mm	dd			

 Number of tablets dispensed

--	--	--	--

Medication Bottle Label

Please attach label from medication dispensed at this visit

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Visit No. 5

Visit

VISITCR

Visit date 2 0 0
year mm dd

Laboratory Assessment

LABCR

Fasting blood sample date 2 0 0
year mm dd

Urine sample date 2 0 0
year mm dd

Study Medication

SACCR

Subject has discontinued study medication due to:

- Study medication has not been discontinued (provide dispensing data below)
- Endpoint
- Initiation of open label statin therapy
- Other reason

Return Accountability from Visit 4

Date returned 2 0 0 Number of tablets returned

Dispensing Accountability at Visit 5

Date dispensed 2 0 0 Number of tablets dispensed

Medication Bottle Label

Please attach label from medication dispensed at this visit

Please attach label from medication dispensed at this visit

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials

F	M	L

Subject No.

--	--	--	--	--

Centre No.

--	--	--	--	--

Visit No. 6

Visit

VISITCR

Visit date

2	0	0			
year	mm	dd			

Laboratory Assessment

LABCR

Fasting blood sample date

2	0	0			
year	mm	dd			

Urine sample date

2	0	0			
year	mm	dd			

Study Medication

SACCR

Subject has discontinued study medication due to:

- Study medication has not been discontinued (provide dispensing data below)
- Endpoint
- Initiation of open label statin therapy
- Other reason

Return Accountability from Visit 5

Date returned

2	0	0			
year	mm	dd			

 Number of tablets returned

--	--	--	--

Dispensing Accountability at Visit 6

Date dispensed

2	0	0			
year	mm	dd			

 Number of tablets dispensed

--	--	--	--

Medication Bottle Label

Please attach label
from medication
dispensed at this
visit

Please attach label
from medication
dispensed at this
visit

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Visit No. 7

Visit

VISITCR

Visit date 2 0 0
year mm dd

Laboratory Assessment

LABCR

Fasting blood sample date 2 0 0
year mm dd

Urine sample date 2 0 0
year mm dd

Study Medication

SACCR

Subject has discontinued study medication due to:

- Study medication has not been discontinued (provide dispensing data below)
- Endpoint
- Initiation of open label statin therapy
- Other reason

Return Accountability from Visit 6

Date returned 2 0 0 Number of tablets returned

Dispensing Accountability at Visit 7

Date dispensed 2 0 0 Number of tablets dispensed

Medication Bottle Label

Please attach label from medication dispensed at this visit

Please attach label from medication dispensed at this visit

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials

F	M	L

Subject No.

--	--	--	--	--

Centre No.

--	--	--	--	--

Visit No. 8

Visit

VISITCR

Visit date

2	0	0			
year	mm	dd			

Laboratory Assessment

LABCR

Fasting blood sample date

2	0	0			
year	mm	dd			

Urine sample date

2	0	0			
year	mm	dd			

Study Medication

SACCR

Subject has discontinued study medication due to:

- Study medication has not been discontinued (provide dispensing data below)
- Endpoint
- Initiation of open label statin therapy
- Other reason

Return Accountability from Visit 7

Date returned

2	0	0			
year	mm	dd			

 Number of tablets returned

--	--	--	--

Dispensing Accountability at Visit 8

Date dispensed

2	0	0			
year	mm	dd			

 Number of tablets dispensed

--	--	--	--

Medication Bottle Label

Please attach label from medication dispensed at this visit

Please attach label from medication dispensed at this visit

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials

F	M	L

Subject No.

--	--	--	--	--

Centre No.

--	--	--	--	--

Visit No. 9

Visit

VISITCR

Visit date

	2	0	0			
	year		mm			dd

Laboratory Assessment

LABCR

Fasting blood sample date

	2	0	0			
	year		mm			dd

Urine sample date

	2	0	0			
	year		mm			dd

Study Medication

SACCR

Subject has discontinued study medication due to:

- Study medication has not been discontinued (provide dispensing data below)
- Endpoint
- Initiation of open label statin therapy
- Other reason

Return Accountability from Visit 8

Date returned

	2	0	0			
	year		mm			dd

 Number of tablets returned

--	--	--	--

Dispensing Accountability at Visit 9

Date dispensed

	2	0	0			
	year		mm			dd

 Number of tablets dispensed

--	--	--	--

Medication Bottle Label

Please attach label
from medication
dispensed at this
visit

Please attach label
from medication
dispensed at this
visit

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials

F	M	L

Subject No.

--	--	--	--	--

Centre No.

--	--	--	--	--

Visit No. 10

Visit

VISITCR

Visit date

2	0	0			
year	mm	dd			

Laboratory Assessment

LABCR

Fasting blood sample date

2	0	0			
year	mm	dd			

Urine sample date

2	0	0			
year	mm	dd			

Study Medication

SACCR

Subject has discontinued study medication due to:

- Study medication has not been discontinued (provide dispensing data below)
- Endpoint
- Initiation of open label statin therapy
- Other reason

Return Accountability from Visit 9

Date returned

2	0	0			
year	mm	dd			

 Number of tablets returned

--	--	--	--

Dispensing Accountability at Visit 10

Date dispensed

2	0	0			
year	mm	dd			

 Number of tablets dispensed

--	--	--	--

Medication Bottle Label

Please attach label from medication dispensed at this visit

Please attach label from medication dispensed at this visit

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials

F	M	L

Subject No.

--	--	--	--	--

Centre No.

--	--	--	--	--

Visit No. 10.1

Visit

VISITCR

Visit date

2	0	0			
year		mm		dd	

Laboratory Assessment

LABCR

Fasting blood sample date

2	0	0			
year		mm		dd	

Urine sample date

2	0	0			
year		mm		dd	

Study Medication

SACCR

Subject has discontinued study medication due to:

- Study medication has not been discontinued (provide dispensing data below)
- Endpoint
- Initiation of open label statin therapy
- Other reason

Return Accountability from Visit 10

Date returned

2	0	0			
year		mm		dd	

 Number of tablets returned

--	--	--	--

Dispensing Accountability at Visit 10.1

Date dispensed

2	0	0			
year		mm		dd	

 Number of tablets dispensed

--	--	--	--

Medication Bottle Label

Please attach label from medication dispensed at this visit

Please attach label from medication dispensed at this visit

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials

F	M	L

Subject No.

--	--	--	--	--

Centre No.

--	--	--	--	--

Visit No. 10.

Visit

VISITCR

Visit date

2	0	0			
year		mm		dd	

Laboratory Assessment

LABCR

Fasting blood sample date

2	0	0			
year		mm		dd	

Urine sample date

2	0	0			
year		mm		dd	

Study Medication

SACCR

Subject has discontinued study medication due to:

- Study medication has not been discontinued (provide dispensing data below)
- Endpoint
- Initiation of open label statin therapy
- Other reason

Return Accountability from Visit 10.

Date returned

2	0	0			
year		mm		dd	

 Number of tablets returned

--	--	--	--

Dispensing Accountability at Visit 10.

Date dispensed

2	0	0			
year		mm		dd	

 Number of tablets dispensed

--	--	--	--

Medication Bottle Label

Please attach label from medication dispensed at this visit

Please attach label from medication dispensed at this visit

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Final Visit

Visit

VISITCR

Visit date
year mm dd

Vital Signs, Weight, Waist circumference

VITCR

Pulse, sitting beats/min

Blood pressure, sitting / mmHg
systolic diastolic

Weight lb

Waist circumference in

Laboratory Assessment

LABCR

Fasting blood sample date
year mm dd

Urine sample date
year mm dd

Study Medication

SACCR

Return Accountability from Visit

Date returned
year mm dd

Number of tablets returned

2003-02-12

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Final Visit

Physical Examination

PHYSCR

Indicate (✓) Normal, Abnormal, or New or Aggravated

	Normal	Abnormal (Same as Visit 2)	New or Aggravated	<i>Describe NEW or AGGRAVATED Abnormalities Only</i>
General Appearance	☐	☐	☐	
Skin	☐	☐	☐	
EENT	☐	☐	☐	
Lymph Nodes	☐	☐	☐	
Endocrine	☐	☐	☐	
Musculoskeletal	☐	☐	☐	
Cardiovascular	☐	☐	☐	
Respiratory	☐	☐	☐	
Central Nervous System	☐	☐	☐	
Gastrointestinal	☐	☐	☐	

NOTE: Record condition of all New or Aggravated Abnormalities on the **Adverse Events** form.

2003-02-12

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Study Completion/Withdrawal

TERMCR

Date of Study completion/withdrawal
year mm dd

Date of last dose
year mm dd

Specify primary reason for study completion/withdrawal:

- Completed study as planned
- Adverse event Please complete the Adverse Event form
- Protocol noncompliance (protocol deviation)
- Subject withdrew consent
- Subject lost to follow-up
- Investigator's discretion
- Other Please specify

Statement of Death

Date of death
year mm dd

Was a postmortem performed
No Yes

Cause of death _____

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Concomitant Therapy

MEDCR

Has the Subject taken any concomitant medication within 30 days prior to Visit 1 and/or during the study?

No Yes

Trade name	Indication	Date Started/Date Stopped (year/mm/dd)	Ongoing
1		<input type="text"/> <input type="text"/>	☐
2		<input type="text"/> <input type="text"/>	☐
3		<input type="text"/> <input type="text"/>	☐
4		<input type="text"/> <input type="text"/>	☐
5		<input type="text"/> <input type="text"/>	☐
6		<input type="text"/> <input type="text"/>	☐
7		<input type="text"/> <input type="text"/>	☐
8		<input type="text"/> <input type="text"/>	☐
9		<input type="text"/> <input type="text"/>	☐
10		<input type="text"/> <input type="text"/>	☐

 If any changes in therapy were made because of an adverse event, please complete the Adverse Event page

2003-02-12

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials

F	M	L	

Subject No.

--	--	--	--	--	--

Centre No.

--	--	--	--	--

Concomitant Therapy

MEDCR

Trade name	Indication	Date Started/Date Stopped (year/mm/dd)	Ongoing																				
1		<table border="1" style="display: inline-table; vertical-align: middle;"><tr><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td></tr><tr><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td></tr></table>																					☐
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 If any changes in therapy were made because of an adverse event, please complete the Adverse Event page

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Adverse Events

AELOGCR

Adverse Event	Follow-up Adverse Event	Date Onset/Resolved (year/mm/dd)	Intensity	Is this a Serious Adverse Event?	Serious*							Outcome to Date	Withdrawn due to event?	Causality Assessment (see question below)	Required Concomitant Therapy?	
					Death	Life-threatening	Inpatient hospitalization or prolongs hospitalization	Persistent or significant disability or incapacity	Congenital abnormality/ Birth defect	Important medical event	Recovered					Ongoing
1.	No ☐ Yes ☐	Onset: 2 0 0 Resolved: 2 0 0	Mild ☐ Moderate ☐ Severe ☐	No ☐ Yes ☐	Death: Yes ☐ Life-threatening: Yes ☐ Inpatient hospitalization or prolongs hospitalization: Yes ☐ Persistent or significant disability or incapacity: Yes ☐ Congenital abnormality/ Birth defect: Yes ☐ Important medical event: Yes ☐	Recovered ☐ Ongoing ☐ Died ☐	No ☐ Yes ☐	If Yes, please complete the concomitant therapy form.								
2.	No ☐ Yes ☐	Onset: 2 0 0 Resolved: 2 0 0	Mild ☐ Moderate ☐ Severe ☐	No ☐ Yes ☐	Death: Yes ☐ Life-threatening: Yes ☐ Inpatient hospitalization or prolongs hospitalization: Yes ☐ Persistent or significant disability or incapacity: Yes ☐ Congenital abnormality/ Birth defect: Yes ☐ Important medical event: Yes ☐	Recovered ☐ Ongoing ☐ Died ☐	No ☐ Yes ☐	If Yes, please complete the concomitant therapy form.								
3.	No ☐ Yes ☐	Onset: 2 0 0 Resolved: 2 0 0	Mild ☐ Moderate ☐ Severe ☐	No ☐ Yes ☐	Death: Yes ☐ Life-threatening: Yes ☐ Inpatient hospitalization or prolongs hospitalization: Yes ☐ Persistent or significant disability or incapacity: Yes ☐ Congenital abnormality/ Birth defect: Yes ☐ Important medical event: Yes ☐	Recovered ☐ Ongoing ☐ Died ☐	No ☐ Yes ☐	If Yes, please complete the concomitant therapy form.								

*If any of the above are YES, please contact your monitor and complete SAE form.

Causality assessment: In your medical judgement, is there a reasonable possibility that the event may have been caused by the randomized therapy?

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials

F	M	L

Subject No.

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Centre No.

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Investigator's Signature**SIGNCR**

The investigator's signature on this page verifies that he/she has reviewed all data recorded on the case report form pages.

The investigator has also reviewed all laboratory findings throughout the study and has reported all laboratory findings considered Adverse Events in accordance with protocol guidance as clinically appropriate.

2	0	0			
year	mm	dd			

.....
Investigator's signature

2003-02-12

Section 5.3.5.1.1 /p.74

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Visit No.

Visit

VISITCR

Visit date
year mm dd

Unscheduled Laboratory Assessment

LABCR

Fasting blood sample date
year mm dd

Urine sample date
year mm dd

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials

F	M	L

Subject No.

--	--	--	--

Centre No.

--	--	--	--

Visit No. ___

Visit

VISITCR

Visit date

2	0	0			
year			mm		

Unscheduled Laboratory Assessment

LABCR

Fasting blood sample date

2	0	0			
year			mm		

Urine sample date

2	0	0			
year			mm		

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Visit No.

Visit

VISITCR

Visit date 2 0 0
year mm dd

Unscheduled Study Medication

SACCR

Return Accountability from Visit

Date returned 2 0 0
year mm dd

Number of tablets returned

Dispensing Accountability at Visit

Date dispensed 2 0 0
year mm dd

Number of tablets dispensed

Medication Bottle Label

Please attach label
from medication
dispensed at this
visit

Please attach label
from medication
dispensed at this
visit

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Visit No. ___

Visit

VISITCR

Visit date 2 0 0
year mm dd

Unscheduled Study Medication

SACCR

Return Accountability from Visit ___

Date returned 2 0 0
year mm dd

Number of tablets returned

Dispensing Accountability at Visit ___

Date dispensed 2 0 0
year mm dd

Number of tablets dispensed

Medication Bottle Label

Please attach label
from medication
dispensed at this
visit

Please attach label
from medication
dispensed at this
visit

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Nonfatal Myocardial Infarction Report

NMIR_CR

Clintrace number _____

Date of admission to hospital Not admitted to hospital
year mm dd

Date of discharge Not discharged
year mm dd

Discharge location If other (7), please specify _____

Did this period of hospitalization include a stay in a critical care unit (ICU, CCU)? No Yes If Yes, number of days

Did this period of hospitalization include a stay in a critical care step down unit? No Yes If Yes, number of days

Diagnosis of Myocardial Infarction

Date of diagnosis of myocardial infarction
year mm dd

Clinical Presentations

Ischemic chest pain greater than 15 minutes within the preceding 48 hours No Yes
Pulmonary edema of ischemic etiology
Cardiogenic shock

Critical Event Enzymes (from local lab tests)

Enzyme	Date of assessment	Enzyme unit
CK	<input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> year mm dd	Peak value <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/>
		Lab upper limit normal range <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> _____
CKMB	<input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> year mm dd	Peak value <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/>
		Lab upper limit normal range <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> _____
Troponin specify:		
I ☐	<input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> year mm dd	Peak value <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/>
T ☐		Lab upper limit normal range <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> _____

ECG Findings No Yes
New Q wave formation (> 0.04 seconds in 2 contiguous leads)
New ischemic ST-T changes (including ST-T elevation (>1 mm) or ST depression (>0.5 mm) and/or persistent T-wave inversion (≥3.0 mm)
New left bundle branch block

Principal Investigator Signature: _____ Date of report: _____

2003-03-27

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Arterial Revascularization Report

ARR_CR

Clintrace number _____

Date of admission to hospital
year mm dd

Not admitted to hospital

Date of discharge
year mm dd

Not discharged

Discharge location

If other (7), please specify _____

Did this period of hospitalization include a stay in a critical care unit (ICU, CCU)?

No

Yes

If Yes, number of days

Did this period of hospitalization include a stay in a critical care step down unit?

No

Yes

If Yes, number of days

Arterial Revascularization

Date of Arterial Revascularization or date of attempted Arterial Revascularization (if failed)
year mm dd

CV Procedures (check all that apply)

Coronary artery bypass grafting

Percutaneous transluminal coronary revascularization with / without stent

Carotid angioplasty with / without stent

Peripheral artery revascularization (not including renal artery) or aneurysm repair

Indicate vessel applicable:

Aorta

Iliac

Femoral

Popliteal

Amputations due to complications of atherosclerosis

Other cardiovascular procedure/operation

Specify: _____

Principal Investigator Signature: _____ Date of report: _____

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Cardiovascular / Cerebrovascular Death Report

CCDR_CR

Clintrace number _____

Date of death
year mm dd

Cause of death

- Myocardial infarction
- Unstable angina
- Sudden death

If sudden death, check all that apply below:

- Death witnessed
- Subject seen alive within 24 hrs of death
- Known arrhythmic death

- Stroke (hemorrhagic)
- Stroke (ischemic)
- Stroke (unknown type)
- Procedure related, including revascularization
- Other cardiovascular death of unknown etiology

Specify: _____

Specify: _____

continues

2003-03-27

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Cardiovascular / Cerebrovascular Death Report (continued)

CCDR_CR

Was an autopsy/post mortem performed? No Yes If Yes, ensure autopsy report is obtained

If Yes, are the findings available at the time of this reporting? No Yes

Prior to his/her death, and since his/her previous visit, had the Subject:

1. Been admitted to hospital? No Yes If Yes, date of admission
2 | 0 | 0 | | | |
year mm dd

Did this period of hospitalization include a stay in a critical care unit (ICU, CCU)? No Yes If Yes, number of days

Did this period of hospitalization include a stay in a critical care step down unit? No Yes If Yes, number of days

2. Undergone a CV operation or procedure (e.g. CABG, PTCA)? No Yes

3. Experienced any other SAE (see definition)? No Yes

Principal Investigator Signature: _____ Date of report: _____

2003-03-27

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Nonfatal Stroke Report

NSR_CR

Clintrace number _____

Date of admission to hospital
year mm dd

Not admitted to hospital

Date of discharge
year mm dd

Not discharged

Discharge location

If other (7), please specify _____

Did this period of hospitalization include a stay in a critical care unit (ICU, CCU)?

No Yes

If Yes, number of days

Did this period of hospitalization include a stay in a critical care step down unit?

If Yes, number of days

Stroke

Date of stroke onset
year mm dd

No Yes

If No, report as an SAE/AE for Transient Ischemic Attack

Was the Subject symptomatic for >24 hours?

Diagnosis of Stroke

Was a diagnostic investigation performed? No Yes

If Yes, check all that apply and provide dates below:

- Computerized tomography (CT) scan
- Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI)
- Arteriography
- Transcranial Doppler

Location and duration of stroke (check one box only)

- Stroke in a new location
- Worsening of previous deficit

If worsening, specify duration below

- Duration > 1 week
- Duration > 24 hrs

On which side of the brain is the stroke?

- Right hemisphere
- Left hemisphere
- Brainstem
- Other

Specify _____

Principal Investigator Signature: _____ Date of report: _____

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Unstable Angina Requiring Hospitalization Report

UARHR_CR

Clintrac number _____

Date of admission to hospital
year mm dd

Date of discharge Not discharged
year mm dd

Discharge location If other (7), please specify _____

Did this period of hospitalization include a stay in a critical care unit (ICU, CCU)? No Yes If Yes, number of days

Did this period of hospitalization include a stay in a critical care step down unit? No Yes If Yes, number of days

Unstable Angina Diagnosis

Date of event onset
year mm dd

Symptoms

Was there evidence of ischemic chest pain at rest or with minimal exertion? No Yes

Was there a change in the usual symptom pattern within the preceding 48 hours requiring hospitalization? No Yes

Evidence of Myocardial Ischemia

Was there a new and/or dynamic ST depression (>0.5 mm), elevation (>1mm) or T wave inversion (≥3.0 mm) on resting ECG No Yes

Was there a definite persistent or reversible wall motion abnormality or scintigraphic perfusion defect demonstrated either spontaneously or by stress testing? No Yes

Was there angiographic evidence of an epicardial coronary artery stenosis of ≥80% diameter reduction (or >50% for the left main coronary artery) and/or evidence for intraluminal arterial thrombus? No Yes

Was there a transient elevation of serum CK, CK-MB, troponin, or any other accepted marker of myocardial ischemia to a level greater than normal but less than the locally defined decision level for the diagnosis of MI? No Yes

Principal Investigator Signature: _____ Date of report: _____

2003-03-27

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Secondary Endpoint Report

SERDV_CR

Deep Vein Thrombosis

Date of diagnosis 2 0 0
year mm dd Not Applicable

Confirmed by diagnostic study: (Check all that were performed)

Doppler	No ☐	Yes ☐	MRI	No ☐	Yes ☐	Please Specify: _____
Venographic Study	☐	☐	Other	☐	☐	
Compression Ultrasound	☐	☐				

Site of Deep Vein Thrombosis: (Check all that apply)

☐ Left Leg	☐ Right Leg	☐ Other specify: _____
☐ proximal with calf	☐ proximal with calf	
☐ proximal without calf	☐ proximal without calf	
☐ calf only	☐ calf only	

Pulmonary Embolism

Date of diagnosis 2 0 0
year mm dd Not Applicable

Confirmed by diagnostic study: (Check all that were performed)

Ventilation perfusion scan	No ☐	Yes ☐	Echocardiogram	No ☐	Yes ☐
Pulmonary angiogram	☐	☐	CT	☐	☐

Site of Pulmonary Embolism: (Check all that apply)

☐ Left Lung	☐ Right Lung
☐ upper lobe	☐ upper lobe
☐ lower lobe	☐ middle lobe
	☐ lower lobe

Principal Investigator Signature: _____ Date of report: _____

2003-03-27

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials

F	M	L

Subject No.

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Centre No.

--	--	--	--	--

Secondary Endpoint Report

SERDM_CR

Diabetes Mellitus

Date of diagnosis

2	0	0			
year	mm	dd			

Diagnosis confirmed by: (Check all that are applicable)

	No	Yes
New use of insulin	☐	☐
New use of oral hypoglycemic agent	☐	☐
Positive glucose tolerance test $\geq$ 200 mg/dL at 2 hours	☐	☐
Repeated fasting glucose $>$ 126 mg/dL (7.0 mmol/L)	☐	☐
Random blood sugar $\geq$ 200 mg/dL associated with symptoms of polyuria, polydipsia, and unexplained weight loss	☐	☐

Principal Investigator Signature: _____ Date of report: _____

2003-03-27

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Secondary Endpoint Report

SERBF_CR

Bone Fractures

Date of diagnosis
year mm dd

Confirmed by diagnostic study: (Check all that were performed)

	No	Yes
X-ray	☐	☐
CT	☐	☐
Bone scan	☐	☐
Other	☐	☐

Please specify: _____

Site of fracture:

- Wrist
- Hip
- Ankle
- Vertebral
- Other Please specify: _____

Principal Investigator Signature: _____ Date of report: _____

2003-03-27

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials

F	M	L

Subject No.

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Centre No.

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Principal Investigator's Signature

SIGNCR

The investigator's signature on this page verifies that he/she has reviewed all data recorded on the case report form pages.

The investigator has also reviewed all laboratory findings throughout the study and has reported all laboratory findings considered Adverse Events in accordance with protocol guidance as clinically appropriate.

2	0			
year	mm	dd		

Principal Investigator's signature

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Clinical Events Adjudication Form

CEAF_CR

Event(s) and Date of Event

Date of event
year mm dd

- | | |
|--|---|
| ☐ Non-fatal myocardial infarction | ☐ Non-fatal stroke |
| ☐ Arterial revascularization | ☐ Cardiovascular / Cerebrovascular death |
| ☐ Unstable angina requiring hospitalization | |

Was this event adjudicated to be a clinical event? No Yes

Non-Fatal Myocardial Infarction

Did the Subject have a Myocardial Infarction? No Yes

If Yes, date and time of myocardial Infarction
year mm dd 24-hour clock

Check only one: Non-procedural related Peri-PCI Peri-CABG

Check only one: Q-wave Non-Q-wave

Provide the following: Peak CK _____ CK-ULN _____ Not Done

Peak CK-MB _____ CK-MB ULN _____ Not Done

Peak troponin _____ Troponin ULN _____ Not Done

Unstable Angina Requiring Hospitalization

Did the Subject have unstable angina requiring hospitalization? No Yes

If Yes, date of hospitalization
year mm dd

Arterial Revascularization

Did the Subject have an arterial revascularization? No Yes

If Yes, date of procedure
year mm dd

- Check only one: PCI Coronary Carotid Peripheral
- Surgical Coronary Carotid Peripheral

continues

2003-03-27

INSTRUCTIONS FOR THE INVESTIGATOR

Clinical Endpoint - Nonfatal Myocardial Infarction

- ◆ Complete the Clinical Endpoint CRF pages and submit with verifying ancillary documentation within 5 business days.
- ◆ Hospitalization - record the dates of admission and discharge. Record the Discharge Location (where the Subject was sent after discharge) from the following list:
 - 1 = Home
 - 2 = Nursing Home
 - 3 = Rehabilitation Facility
 - 4 = Hospital Transfer
 - 5 = Deceased
 - 6 = Not discharged at study termination/completion
 - 7 = Other (please specify)
- ◆ Record the date of diagnosis of myocardial infarction
- ◆ Indicate 'Yes' or 'No' for clinical presentations. Please do not leave any blanks.
- ◆ Record the **peak** critical "event" diagnosing cardiac enzyme for CK, CKMB, and/or Troponin from local laboratory reports
- ◆ Record the ECG findings
- ◆ If the Subject has experienced a primary clinical endpoint, discontinue the Subject from study therapy. Continue to redraw out of range labs until values return to baseline (capture on the Unscheduled Laboratory CRF pages).
- ◆ Review and record concomitant medications
- ◆ Obtain Principal Investigator's signature and date
- ◆ Schedule Subject's next protocol visit according to their visit schedule

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Nonfatal Myocardial Infarction Report

NMIR_CR

Date of admission to hospital
year mm dd Not admitted to hospital

Date of discharge
year mm dd Not discharged

Discharge location If other (7), please specify _____

Did this period of hospitalization include a stay in a critical care unit (ICU, CCU)?
No Yes If Yes, number of days

Did this period of hospitalization include a stay in a critical care step down unit?
No Yes If Yes, number of days

Diagnosis of Myocardial Infarction

Date of diagnosis of myocardial infarction
year mm dd

Clinical Presentations

Ischemic chest pain greater than 15 minutes within the preceding 48 hours
No Yes

Pulmonary edema of ischemic etiology
No Yes

Cardiogenic shock
No Yes

Critical Event Enzymes (from local lab tests)

Enzyme	Date of assessment	Enzyme unit
CK	<input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> year mm dd	Peak value <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/>
		Lab upper limit normal range <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/>
CKMB	<input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> year mm dd	Peak value <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/>
		Lab upper limit normal range <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/>
Troponin specify:		
I ☐	<input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> year mm dd	Peak value <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/>
T ☐		Lab upper limit normal range <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/>

ECG Findings

New Q wave formation (> 0.04 seconds in 2 contiguous leads) No Yes

New ischemic ST-T changes (including ST-T elevation (>1 mm) or ST depression (>0.5 mm) and/or persistent T-wave inversion (≥3.0 mm) No Yes

New left bundle branch block No Yes

Principal Investigator Signature: _____ Date of report: _____

INSTRUCTIONS FOR THE INVESTIGATOR

Clinical Endpoint - Arterial Revascularization Report

- ◆ Complete the Clinical Endpoint CRF pages and submit with verifying ancillary documentation within 5 business days.
- ◆ Hospitalization - record the dates of admission and discharge. Record the Discharge Location (where the Subject was sent after discharge) from the following list:
 - 1 = Home
 - 2 = Nursing Home
 - 3 = Rehabilitation Facility
 - 4 = Hospital Transfer
 - 5 = Deceased
 - 6 = Not discharged at study termination/completion
 - 7 = Other (please specify)
- ◆ Record the date the revascularization procedure was performed or the date that revascularization was attempted (if failed)
- ◆ Indicate the cardiovascular procedure performed by checking all appropriate boxes
- ◆ If a peripheral revascularization was performed, please indicate which vessel(s) was revascularized
- ◆ If the Subject has experienced a primary clinical endpoint, discontinue the Subject from study therapy. Continue to redraw out of range labs until values return to pre-procedure baseline values (capture on the Unscheduled Laboratory CRF pages).
- ◆ Review and record concomitant medications
- ◆ Obtain Principal Investigator's signature and date
- ◆ Schedule Subject's next protocol visit according to their visit schedule

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Arterial Revascularization Report

ARR_CR

Date of admission to hospital 2 0
year mm dd

Not admitted to hospital

Date of discharge 2 0
year mm dd

Not discharged

Discharge location

If other (7), please specify _____

Did this period of hospitalization include a stay in a critical care unit (ICU, CCU)?

No Yes

If Yes, number of days

Did this period of hospitalization include a stay in a critical care step down unit?

No Yes

If Yes, number of days

Arterial Revascularization

Date of Arterial Revascularization or date of attempted Arterial Revascularization (if failed) 2 0
year mm dd

CV Procedures (check all that apply)

Coronary artery bypass grafting

Percutaneous transluminal coronary revascularization with / without stent

Carotid angioplasty with / without stent

Peripheral artery revascularization (not including renal artery) or aneurysm repair

Indicate vessel applicable:

Aorta

Iliac

Femoral

Popliteal

Amputations due to complications of atherosclerosis

Other cardiovascular procedure/operation

Specify: _____

Principal Investigator Signature: _____ Date of report: _____

INSTRUCTIONS FOR THE INVESTIGATOR

Clinical Endpoint - Cardiovascular / Cerebrovascular Death Report

- Complete the Clinical Endpoint CRF pages and submit with verifying ancillary documentation within 5 business days.
- Record the date of death
- Record the cause of death
- Obtain autopsy report if performed
- Record hospitalization information
- Obtain Principal Investigator's signature and date

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Cardiovascular / Cerebrovascular Death Report

CCDR_CR

Date of death
year mm dd

Cause of death

- Myocardial infarction
- Unstable angina
- Sudden death

If sudden death, check all that apply below:

- Death witnessed
- Subject seen alive within 24 hrs of death
- Known arrhythmic death

- Stroke (hemorrhagic)
- Stroke (ischemic)
- Stroke (unknown type)
- Procedure related, including revascularization
- Other cardiovascular death of unknown etiology

Specify: _____

Specify: _____

continues

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials

F	M	L

Subject No.

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Centre No.

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Cardiovascular / Cerebrovascular Death Report (continued)

CCDR_CR

Was an autopsy/post mortem performed?

No	Yes
☐	☐

 If Yes, ensure autopsy report is obtained

If Yes, are the findings available at the time of this reporting?

No	Yes
☐	☐

Prior to his/her death, and since his/her previous visit, had the Subject:

1. Been admitted to hospital?

No	Yes
☐	☐

 If Yes, date of admission

2	0								

year mm dd

Did this period of hospitalization include a stay in a critical care unit (ICU, CCU)?

No	Yes
☐	☐

 If Yes, number of days

--	--	--	--

Did this period of hospitalization include a stay in a critical care step down unit?

No	Yes
☐	☐

 If Yes, number of days

--	--	--	--

2. Undergone a CV operation or procedure (e.g. CABG, PTCA)?

No	Yes
☐	☐

3. Experienced any other SAE (see definition)?

No	Yes
☐	☐

Investigator Signature: _____ Date of report: _____

Section 5.3.5.1.1 /p.96

INSTRUCTIONS FOR THE INVESTIGATOR

Clinical Endpoint - Nonfatal Stroke Report

- ◆ Complete the Clinical Endpoint CRF pages and submit with verifying ancillary documentation within 5 business days.
- ◆ Hospitalization - record the dates of admission and discharge. Record the Discharge Location (where the Subject was sent after discharge) from the following list:
 - 1 = Home
 - 2 = Nursing Home
 - 3 = Rehabilitation Facility
 - 4 = Hospital Transfer
 - 5 = Deceased
 - 6 = Not discharged at study termination/completion
 - 7 = Other (please specify)
- ◆ Record date of stroke onset
- ◆ Record whether Subject had symptoms lasting longer than 24 hours, if less than 24 hours, report this event as an SAE/AE of Transient Ischemic Attack - not as an endpoint
- ◆ Record diagnostic information
- ◆ Record location and duration of stroke
- ◆ If the Subject has experienced a primary clinical endpoint, discontinue the Subject from study therapy.
- ◆ Review and record concomitant medications
- ◆ Obtain Principal Investigator's signature and date
- ◆ Schedule Subject's next protocol visit according to their visit schedule

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Nonfatal Stroke Report

NSR_CR

Date of admission to hospital

2 0
year mm dd

Not admitted to hospital

Date of discharge

2 0
year mm dd

Not discharged

Discharge location

If other (7), please specify _____

Did this period of hospitalization include a stay in a critical care unit (ICU, CCU)?

No Yes

If Yes, number of days

Did this period of hospitalization include a stay in a critical care step down unit?

If Yes, number of days

Stroke

Date of stroke onset

2 0
year mm dd

No Yes

If No, report as an SAE/AE for Transient Ischemic Attack

Was the Subject symptomatic for >24 hours?

Diagnosis of Stroke

No Yes

Was a diagnostic investigation performed?

If Yes, check all that apply and provide dates below:

Computerized tomography (CT) scan

2 0
year mm dd

Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI)

2 0
year mm dd

Arteriography

2 0
year mm dd

Transcranial Doppler

2 0
year mm dd

Location and duration of stroke (check one box only)

Stroke in a new location

Worsening of previous deficit

If worsening, specify duration below

Duration > 1 week

Duration > 24 hrs

On which side of the brain is the stroke?

Right hemisphere

Left hemisphere

Brainstem

Other

Specify _____

Principal Investigator Signature: _____

Date of report: _____

INSTRUCTIONS FOR THE INVESTIGATOR

Clinical Endpoint - Unstable Angina Requiring Hospitalization Report

- ◆ Complete the Clinical Endpoint CRF pages and submit with verifying ancillary documentation within 5 business days.
- ◆ If the Subject was not admitted to a hospital bed or did not have objective evidence of ischemia, the event does not constitute a Clinical Endpoint
- ◆ Hospitalization - record the dates of admission and discharge. Record the Discharge Location (where the Subject was sent after discharge) from the following list:
 - 1 = Home
 - 2 = Nursing Home
 - 3 = Rehabilitation Facility
 - 4 = Hospital Transfer
 - 5 = Deceased
 - 6 = Not discharged at study termination/completion
 - 7 = Other (please specify)
- ◆ Record date of onset of unstable angina
- ◆ Indicate symptoms by checking 'Yes' or 'No' to all that apply
- ◆ Indicate applicable evidence of myocardial ischemia by checking 'Yes' or 'No' for all that apply. Please do not leave any blanks.
- ◆ If the Subject has experienced a primary clinical endpoint, discontinue the Subject from study therapy.
- ◆ Review and record concomitant medications
- ◆ Obtain Principal Investigator's signature and date
- ◆ Schedule Subject's next protocol visit according to their visit schedule

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Unstable Angina Requiring Hospitalization Report

UARHR_CR

Date of admission to hospital 2 0
year mm dd

Date of discharge 2 0 Not discharged
year mm dd

Discharge location If other (7), please specify _____

Did this period of hospitalization include a stay in a critical care unit (ICU, CCU)? No Yes If Yes, number of days

Did this period of hospitalization include a stay in a critical care step down unit? No Yes If Yes, number of days

Unstable Angina Diagnosis

Date of event onset 2 0
year mm dd

Symptoms

Was there evidence of ischemic chest pain at rest or with minimal exertion? No Yes

Was there a change in the usual symptom pattern within the preceding 48 hours requiring hospitalization? No Yes

Evidence of Myocardial Ischemia

Was there a new and/or dynamic ST depression (>0.5 mm), elevation (>1mm) or T wave inversion (≥3.0 mm) on resting ECG No Yes

Was there a definite persistent or reversible wall motion abnormality or scintigraphic perfusion defect demonstrated either spontaneously or by stress testing? No Yes

Was there angiographic evidence of an epicardial coronary artery stenosis of ≥80% diameter reduction (or >50% for the left main coronary artery) and/or evidence for intraluminal arterial thrombus? No Yes

Was there a transient elevation of serum CK, CK-MB, troponin, or any other accepted marker of myocardial ischemia to a level greater than normal but less than the locally defined decision level for the diagnosis of MI? No Yes

Principal Investigator Signature: _____ Date of report: _____

INSTRUCTIONS FOR THE INVESTIGATOR

**Secondary Endpoints of Diabetes Mellitus, Bone Fracture,
Deep Vein Thrombosis and Pulmonary Embolism**

- ◆ Complete the Secondary Endpoint CRF page(s)
- ◆ Document the event as an SAE or Non-Serious AE based on seriousness criteria on the Adverse Events CRF
- ◆ Document the date the diagnosis was made
- ◆ Check Appropriate diagnostic boxes, or if your response is not included, specify
- ◆ Review and record concomitant medications
- ◆ Obtain Principal Investigator's signature and date

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials

F	M	L

Subject No.

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Centre No.

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Secondary Endpoint Report

SERDV_CR

Deep Vein Thrombosis

Date of diagnosis

2	0			
year	mm	dd		

 Not Applicable

Confirmed by diagnostic study: (Check all that were performed)

Doppler	No	Yes		No	Yes	
	☐	☐	MRI	☐	☐	
Venographic Study	☐	☐	Other	☐	☐	Please Specify: _____
Compression Ultrasound	☐	☐				

Site of Deep Vein Thrombosis: (Check all that apply)

☐ Left Leg	☐ Right Leg	☐ Other specify: _____
☐ proximal with calf	☐ proximal with calf	
☐ proximal without calf	☐ proximal without calf	
☐ calf only	☐ calf only	

Pulmonary Embolism

Date of diagnosis

2	0			
year	mm	dd		

 Not Applicable

Confirmed by diagnostic study: (Check all that were performed)

Ventilation perfusion scan	No	Yes		No	Yes
	☐	☐	Echocardiogram	☐	☐
Pulmonary angiogram	☐	☐	CT	☐	☐

Site of Pulmonary Embolism: (Check all that apply)

☐ Left Lung	☐ Right Lung
☐ upper lobe	☐ upper lobe
☐ lower lobe	☐ middle lobe
	☐ lower lobe

Principal Investigator Signature: _____ Date of report: _____

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials

F	M	L

Subject No.

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Centre No.

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Secondary Endpoint Report

SERDM_CR

Diabetes Mellitus

Date of diagnosis

1	2	0				
year	mm	dd				

Diagnosis confirmed by: (Check all that are applicable)

	No	Yes
New use of insulin	☐	☐
New use of oral hypoglycemic agent	☐	☐
Positive glucose tolerance test $\geq$ 200 mg/dL (11.1 mmol/L) at 2 hours	☐	☐
Repeated fasting glucose $>$ 126 mg/dL (7.0 mmol/L)	☐	☐
Random blood sugar $\geq$ 200 mg/dL (11.1 mmol/L) associated with symptoms of polyuria, polydipsia, and unexplained weight loss	☐	☐

Principal Investigator Signature: _____ Date of report: _____

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Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials

F	M	L

Subject No.

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Centre No.

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Secondary Endpoint Report

SERBF_CR

Bone Fractures

Date of diagnosis

2	0				
year		mm		dd	

Confirmed by diagnostic study: (Check all that were performed)

	No	Yes
X-ray	☐	☐
CT	☐	☐
Bone scan	☐	☐
Other	☐	☐

Please specify: _____

Site of fracture: (Check all that apply)

- Wrist
- Hip
- Ankle
- Vertebral
- Other Please specify: _____

Principal Investigator Signature: _____ Date of report: _____

Amended 2006-01-31

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Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Clinical Events Adjudication Form

CEAF_CR

Event(s) and Date of Event

Date of event 2 0
year mm dd

- | | |
|--|---|
| ☐ Non-fatal myocardial infarction | ☐ Non-fatal stroke |
| ☐ Arterial revascularization | ☐ Cardiovascular / Cerebrovascular death |
| ☐ Unstable angina requiring hospitalization | ☐ Non-Cardiovascular / Cerebrovascular death |

Was this event adjudicated to be a clinical event? No Yes

Non-Fatal Myocardial Infarction

Did the Subject have a Myocardial Infarction? No Yes

If Yes, date and time of myocardial infarction 2 0 :
year mm dd 24-hour clock

Check only one: Non-procedural related Peri-PCI Peri-CABG

Check only one: Q-wave Non-Q-wave

Provide the following: Peak CK _____ CK-ULN _____ Not Done

Peak CK-MB _____ CK-MB ULN _____ Not Done

Peak troponin _____ Troponin ULN _____ Not Done

Unstable Angina Requiring Hospitalization

Did the Subject have unstable angina requiring hospitalization? No Yes

If Yes, date of hospitalization 2 0
year mm dd

Arterial Revascularization

Did the Subject have an arterial revascularization? No Yes

If Yes, date of procedure 2 0
year mm dd

Check only one: PCI Coronary Carotid Peripheral

Surgical Coronary Carotid Peripheral

continues

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Clinical Events Adjudication Form (continued)

CEAF_CR

Non-fatal Stroke

Did the Subject have a stroke? No Yes

If Yes, date of stroke
year mm dd

- Check only one:
- Primary hemorrhagic (check only one)
 - Intraparenchymal Intraventricular
 - Subdural Subarachnoid
 - Infarction with hemorrhagic conversion
 - Cerebral infarction
 - Uncertain

Death

Did the Subject die? No Yes

If Yes, date of death
year mm dd

- Check only one:
- Cardiovascular/Cerebrovascular
 - Non-Cardiovascular/NonCerebrovascular

Comments or additional data required: _____

Committee Representative Signature: _____ Date: _____

PPD-PVG notified by: _____ Date and Time: _____ :

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Clinical Events Adjudication Form (continued)

CEAF_CR

Non-fatal Stroke

Did the Subject have a stroke? No Yes

If Yes, date of stroke
year mm dd

- Check only one:
- Primary hemorrhagic (check only one)
 - Intraparenchymal Intraventricular
 - Subdural Subarachnoid
 - Infarction with hemorrhagic conversion
 - Cerebral infarction
 - Uncertain

Death

Did the Subject die? No Yes

If Yes, date of death
year mm dd

- Check only one:
- Cardiovascular/Cerebrovascular
 - Non-Cardiovascular/NonCerebrovascular

Comments or additional data required: _____

Committee Representative Signature: _____ Date: _____

PPD-PVG notified by: _____ Date and Time: _____ :

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Demography

SDEMCR

Date of birth
year mm dd

Date of written consent
year mm dd

Sex

Male
Female

Origin

Caucasian
Black
Asian
Hispanic
Other

Study Withdrawal

STERMCR

Date of withdrawal
year mm dd

Did the Subject have any serious adverse events? No Yes If Yes, complete the Adverse Event form

Check primary reason for withdrawal

- Subject did not meet inclusion/exclusion criteria
- Adverse event (including clinical endpoint)
- Protocol noncompliance (protocol deviation)
- Subject withdrew consent
- Subject lost to follow-up
- Investigator's discretion
- Other Please specify

Investigator's Signature

SSIGNCR

By signing and dating this page, I declare that the information on this CRF and all laboratory data have been reviewed by me or my authorized delegate, and is accurate and complete.

.....
year mm dd Investigator's signature

Screening Packet

Please complete the enclosed Case Report Form (CRF) for each Screen Failure Subject

NOTE:

- ◆ If the Subject is a Screen Failure, only the Screen Failure form SF-1.1 will need to be completed for the Subject.

- ◆ If the Subject has a Serious Adverse Event (SAE), please also complete the Adverse Event form.

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Demography

SDEMCR

Date of birth
year mm dd

Date of written consent
year mm dd

Sex
Male
Female

Origin
Caucasian
Black
Asian
Hispanic
Other

Study Withdrawal

STERMCR

Date of withdrawal
year mm dd

Did the Subject have any serious adverse events? No Yes **If Yes, complete the Adverse Event form**

Check primary reason for withdrawal

		Inclusion Criteria #	Exclusion Criteria #
Subject did not meet inclusion/exclusion criteria	☐	Number of first failed criterion <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/> <input type="text"/>
Adverse event (including clinical endpoint)	☐		
Protocol noncompliance (protocol deviation)	☐		
Subject withdrew consent	☐		
Subject lost to follow-up	☐		
Investigator's discretion	☐		
Other	☐	Please specify	

Investigator's Signature

SSIGNCR

By signing and dating this page, I declare that the information on this CRF and all laboratory data have been reviewed by me or my authorized delegate, and is accurate and complete.

year mm dd Investigator's signature

Study No. 4522US/0011

Subject Initials
F M L

Subject No.

Centre No.

Visit No. VS.____

D0007:11

Subject Vital Status and Other Outcomes

VITSTAT

Date of last known contact/confirmation regarding subject status
year mm dd

Vital Status

Is this Subject alive? Unknown No Yes
 ₂ ₀ ₁

If this Subject is dead:

Was the cause Cardiovascular (including stroke)? Unknown No Yes
 ₂ ₀ ₁

Date of death (if known)
year mm dd

Other Outcomes

Since the last Jupiter contact/confirmation date listed above:

Date if known

Has this Subject had a myocardial infarction? Unknown No Yes
 ₂ ₀ ₁
year mm dd

Has this Subject been hospitalized for unstable angina? Unknown No Yes
 ₂ ₀ ₁
year mm dd

Has this Subject had an arterial revascularization? Unknown No Yes
 ₂ ₀ ₁
year mm dd

Has this Subject had a stroke? Unknown No Yes
 ₂ ₀ ₁
year mm dd

Principal Investigator signature _____
year mm dd

2007-11-26

